

THE LAGRANGIAN FORMULATION WITH AN EXPLICIT GEOMETRICAL INTERPRETATION OF PERTURBATIONS

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February 17, 2025

Abstract

This paper presents the Lagrangian formulation with a precise geometrical interpretation of perturbations. It examines the influence of perturbative forces on the dynamics of a system through a geometric framework. The detailed Euler-Lagrange equation is derived intuitively and explicitly, shedding light on the perturbations and their effects on the system's behavior. This approach provides a deeper understanding of the role of perturbations in dynamical systems. The work establishes a connection between the mathematical structure of the Lagrangian formalism and its geometric interpretation, offering a clearer insight into the underlying physical principles.

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1 Framing the Question: Why Do Physical Systems Behave the Way They Do?

Imagine a cannonball being fired from the origin of a vast, open field. The initial position, $(x_i, y_i) = (0, 0)$, marks the place where the cannon rests. From this point, the cannonball is projected with a force, its initial velocity, $\vec{v}_0 = |\vec{v}_x|\hat{x} + |\vec{v}_y|\hat{y} + |\vec{v}_z|\hat{z}$, and at an angle $0 < \theta < 90^\circ$ relative to the horizontal plane. The cannonball takes flight, soaring into the sky with a sense of direction, carving a path determined by the interplay of forces.

After a certain amount of time has passed, the ball is observed to land at a final position, $(x_f, y_f) = (x, 0)$, on the ground—seemingly a straightforward outcome. However, the story

doesn't end with the ball hitting the ground. The question that arises, hidden beneath the surface of this seemingly simple event, is this: among the infinite number of possible paths—curves that could connect the starting point $(0,0)$ to the final point $(x,0)$ —why does the ball follow one specific path? What governs its journey from the beginning to the end?

In the early days of *Isaac Newton's* work, deriving the trajectory of an object using Newtonian mechanics was relatively straightforward. However, a deeper question arose: why does nature select this particular path over all others? This question intrigued many scholars during *Newton's* time, yet it took some time to establish a formal principle and mathematical framework to explain it.

This principle is known as the *principle of stationary action*, or *Maupertuis's principle*, formulated by *Pierre-Louis Moreau de Maupertuis* (1698 - 27 July 1759) in 1744. It states that the actual path taken by a physical system between two points in its configuration space is the one for which the action is stationary—typically a minimum. This principle forms the foundation of much of classical mechanics and has profound implications, influencing both classical and modern physics.

Building upon this idea, *Joseph-Louis Lagrange* (25 January 1736 - 10 April 1813) developed a new formulation of mechanics, called *Lagrangian mechanics*, in 1788, introduced in his book *Mécanique Analytique*. This formulation elegantly describes physical systems using the principle of stationary action, providing a powerful alternative to *Newton's* laws.

2 The Explicit Derivation of Euler-Lagrangian Equation

Consider the simple case of a particle moving along a single spatial dimension. Its initial state is given by a pair of coordinates (x_i, t_i) , representing its position at time t_i , or alternatively, by the pair (x_i, \dot{x}_i) , representing its initial position and velocity. As time progresses, the particle interacts with its surroundings, and its state may change. After some period, defined by $T = t_f - t_i$, we are left with the final state of the particle, described by the coordinates (x_f, t_f) , or equivalently, by (x_f, \dot{x}_f) , where x_f is the final position and \dot{x}_f is the final velocity.

The question then arises: how does the particle move between its initial and final states? There are infinitely many possible paths the particle could take, each with its own distinct characteristics. Yet, the particle follows just one specific path that satisfies the conditions governing the system. The task, then, is to determine which path the particle takes.

To address this, we introduce a mathematical framework. For every possible trajectory, we assign a unique number $S \in \mathbb{R}$, known as the action. Since there are infinitely many paths, there will be infinitely many values of S , each corresponding to a different path.

The action quantifies the properties of each trajectory. Importantly, the action depends not just on distance or time, but on the unique characteristics of the path itself.

To identify the correct path—the one the particle actually follows—we need to determine which specific value of S corresponds to this true trajectory. This task involves assigning the action S to each path based on its unique features, then identifying which value of S corresponds to the path the particle actually takes. The true path is not chosen at random; rather, it is determined by the inherent properties of the system, governed by the laws of nature.

The mathematical framework that governs the particle's motion incorporates both the unique properties of each trajectory and the criterion for selecting the true path. The correct path is determined by a specific action, which is intrinsic to the path itself, independent of any external conditions or subjective assumptions.

Consider a functional, specifically the action functional $S[x(t)]$, which is a function of the trajectory $x(t)$ and is defined as the integral of a function L , depending on time t , position $x(t)$, and velocity $\dot{x}(t)$, over the interval from the initial time t_i to the final time t_f :

$$S[x(t)] = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.1})$$

We aim to find the function $x(t)$ that makes $S[x(t)]$ stationary. Before we proceed with the derivation, let's first examine graphically what we mean by stationary. To do this, consider the following graphs.

In the first graph, we plot the function $y = x(t)$. In the second graph, we plot $x(t)$ on the x -axis and $S[x(t)]$ on the y -axis. This graph illustrates how $S[x(t)]$ changes as $x(t)$ varies.

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In the third graph, we perturb the functional input $x(t)$ by adding a small perturbation $\varepsilon\eta(x)$, so the new input becomes $x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t)$. This perturbed value is plotted on the x -axis, while the y -axis shows the output $S[x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t)]$.

The difference in the y -values between the third and second graphs at corresponding points represents the change in $S[x(t)]$, and dividing by the infinitesimally small distance ε between these two planes gives the slope, or the derivative, at that point. Graphing these slopes on the y -axis and $x(t)$ on the x -axis in the fourth graph gives us the rate of change of $S[x(t)]$ with respect to $x(t)$.

Notice that in the fourth graph, there could be one or multiple maxima, minima, or saddle points where the slope or derivative is zero. Mathematically, this corresponds to

the generalized condition known as the stationary condition.

$$\left. \frac{dF}{d\varepsilon} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.2})$$

This is achieved by considering a small perturbation to $x(t)$, introducing a new trajectory $\bar{x}(t)$ defined as

$$\bar{x}(t) = x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t), \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.3})$$

where ε is a small parameter, and $\eta(t)$ is an arbitrary smooth function such that $\eta(t_i) = \eta(t_f) = 0$. The perturbed velocity is then given by

$$\dot{\bar{x}}(t) = \dot{x}(t) + \varepsilon\dot{\eta}(t). \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.4})$$

Next, we compute the functional derivative $\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)}$, which describes the variation of the action with respect to small changes in $x(t)$. This is defined as

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{S[x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t)] - S[x(t)]}{\varepsilon} \right]. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.5})$$

Substituting the expression for $S[x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t)]$, we get

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} L(t, x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t), \dot{x}(t) + \varepsilon\dot{\eta}(t)) dt \right) - \left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt \right)}{\varepsilon} \right]. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.6})$$

To proceed, we expand the Lagrangian L in a Taylor series about (x, \dot{x}) to first order in ε :

$$L(t, x(t) + \varepsilon\eta(t), \dot{x}(t) + \varepsilon\dot{\eta}(t)) = L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} \eta(t) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \dot{\eta}(t) + O(\varepsilon^2). \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.7})$$

Substituting this expansion into the expression for $\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)}$, we obtain

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} (L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t))) + \left(\varepsilon \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} \eta(t) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \dot{\eta}(t) \right) dt \right) - \left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt \right)}{\varepsilon} \right]. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.8})$$

Simplifying, this becomes

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} \eta(t) + \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \dot{\eta}(t) \right) dt. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.9})$$

To handle the second term, we use integration by parts:

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \left\{ \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} \eta(t) dt \right\} + \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \eta(t) \right]_{t_i}^{t_f} - \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) \eta(t) dt \right\}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.10})$$

Since $\eta(t_i) = \eta(t_f) = 0$, the boundary term vanishes, leaving

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) \eta(t) dt. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.11})$$

For the action to be stationary, we require $\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = 0$ for any arbitrary function $\eta(t)$. This implies that the integrand must vanish identically, leading to the following equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} = 0}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.12})$$

Alternatively, multiplying both sides by -1 , we obtain

$$\boxed{\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0}. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.13})$$

This is derived from the variational principles introduced by *Leonard Euler* (15 April 1707 – 18 September 1784) and later applied to physical systems by *Joseph-Louis Lagrange* (25 January 1736 – 10 April 1813), and hence is known as the Euler-Lagrange equation. The function L is called the Lagrangian, which is yet to be determined, and it determines the path or trajectory of a system.

The action functional $S[x(t)]$ attains a stationary value for any function L , provided that

$x(t)$ satisfies the corresponding Euler-Lagrange equation. In general, there can be multiple possible functions L (Lagrangians) that satisfy the Euler-Lagrange equation for a given physical system. Look at the following example.

Consider a system where the mass $m(t)$ is a function of time. The Lagrangian can be written as:

$$L_{\text{arbitrary}} = \frac{1}{2}m(t)\dot{x}^2 - U(x) + \frac{d}{dt}f(x, \dot{x}, t) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.14})$$

Here, $m(t)$ is the time-dependent mass, $U(x)$ is the potential energy, and $f(x, \dot{x}, t)$ is an arbitrary function. The Euler-Lagrange equation is:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L_{\text{arbitrary}}}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) - \frac{\partial L_{\text{arbitrary}}}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.15})$$

Now, we compute the necessary derivatives for the Lagrangian. First, the partial derivative of the Lagrangian with respect to \dot{x} :

$$\frac{\partial L_{\text{arbitrary}}}{\partial \dot{x}} = m(t)\dot{x} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial \dot{x}^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.16})$$

Next, the partial derivative with respect to x :

$$\frac{\partial L_{\text{arbitrary}}}{\partial x} = -\frac{dU}{dx} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.17})$$

Substitute these into the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(m(t)\dot{x} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial \dot{x}^2} \right) - \left(-\frac{dU}{dx} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.18})$$

Taking the time derivative of $m(t)\dot{x} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial \dot{x}^2}$:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(m(t)\dot{x} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial \dot{x}^2} \right) = m(t)\ddot{x} + \dot{x} \frac{dm(t)}{dt} + \frac{\partial^3 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial t \partial \dot{x}^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.19})$$

Thus, the Euler-Lagrange equation becomes:

$$\boxed{m(t)\ddot{x} + \dot{x} \frac{dm(t)}{dt} + \frac{\partial^3 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial t \partial \dot{x}^2} + \frac{dU}{dx} - \frac{\partial^2 f(x, \dot{x}, t)}{\partial x \partial \dot{x}} = 0} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.20})$$

This may or may not represent the equations of motion.

However, the fundamental equations of motion derived from the Euler-Lagrange equation must be equivalent to the physical laws governing the system, such as Newton's laws in classical mechanics.

Now, there exists only one function L for which this Euler-Lagrange equation holds in

determining the path of the particle. In other words, this is the function that reformulates Newton's laws.

Hence, we proceed by asking directly: what is the form of the function L that, when plugged into the Euler-Lagrangian equation, results in describing Newton's laws? One can easily recognize that it must be a function involving the difference between the kinetic T and potential U energies:

$$L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) = T - U \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.21})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}m(t)\dot{x}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.22})$$

Substitute this in the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{x}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) - \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{\vec{x}}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) \right] = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.23})$$

First, compute the derivatives, for first term:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{x}} \left(\frac{1}{2}m(t)\dot{x}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) = -\frac{dU}{dx} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.24})$$

and for the second term:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{\vec{x}}} \left(\frac{1}{2}m(t)\dot{x}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) = m(t)\dot{x} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.25})$$

Now, taking the total time derivative:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(m(t)\dot{x}(t) \right) = \frac{dm(t)}{dt}\dot{x} + m(t)\ddot{x}(t) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.26})$$

Substitute these into the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$-\frac{dU}{dx} - \left(\frac{dm(t)}{dt}\dot{x}(t) + m(t)\ddot{x}(t) \right) = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.27})$$

This simplifies to:

$$m(t)\ddot{x}(t) + \frac{dm(t)}{dt}\dot{x}(t) = -\frac{dU}{dx} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.28})$$

The LHS is nothing but the second-order differential equation for force acting on a body whose mass is time dependent. That is:

$$\vec{F} = -\frac{dU}{dx} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.29})$$

Thus, choosing the Lagrangian $L = T - U$ represents the equations of motion.

We rewrite the full form of the Euler-Lagrangian equation by substituting the solution L , for a single particle moving in one dimension:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{x}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{\vec{x}}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) - \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{\vec{x}}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{\vec{x}}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) \right]} = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.30})$$

Or equivalently we obtain by multiplying -1 on both sides:

$$\boxed{\frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{\vec{x}}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{\vec{x}}^2 - U(\vec{x}(t)) \right) \right] - \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{x}} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{\vec{x}}^2 - U(\vec{x}) \right)} = 0. \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.31})$$

Since we know the form of the Lagrangian L , on substituting this in the action $S[x(t)]$ must get the same result as follows:

$$S[x(t)] = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} L(t, x(t), \dot{x}(t)) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.32})$$

$$= \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(x(t)) \right) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.33})$$

$$= \left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 dt \right) - \left(\int_{t_i}^{t_f} U(x(t)) dt \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.34})$$

Now, we calculate the variation of the action:

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{S[x + \varepsilon \eta] - S[x]}{\varepsilon} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.35})$$

$$= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) (\dot{x}(t) - \varepsilon \dot{\eta}(t))^2 - U(x(t) - \varepsilon \eta(t)) \right) dt \right) - \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(x(t)) \right) dt \right)}{\varepsilon} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.36})$$

Expanding the kinetic term $\frac{1}{2} m(t) (\dot{x} - \varepsilon \dot{\eta}(t))^2$:

$$\frac{1}{2} m(t) (\dot{x}(t) - \varepsilon \dot{\eta}(t))^2 = \frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - \varepsilon m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t) + O(\varepsilon^2) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.37})$$

Expanding the potential term $U(x - \varepsilon \eta(t))$ to first order in ε :

$$U(x - \varepsilon \eta(t)) = U(x) - \varepsilon \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} + O(\varepsilon^2) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.38})$$

Now subtract the second integral $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(x) \right) dt$:

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - \varepsilon m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t) - U(x) + \varepsilon \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} \right) dt \right) - \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} m(t) \dot{x}^2 - U(x) \right) dt \right)}{\varepsilon} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.39})$$

$$= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\left(-\varepsilon \int_{t_1}^{t_2} m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t) dt \right) + \left(\varepsilon \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} dt \right)}{\varepsilon} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.40})$$

$$= \left(- \int_{t_1}^{t_2} m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t) dt \right) + \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} dt \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.41})$$

We now perform integration by parts on the term $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} (m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t)) dt$. Using the formula for integration by parts:

$$\int u dv = uv - \int v du \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.42})$$

Let's choose:

1. $u = m(t) \dot{x}$, so $du = m(t) \ddot{x} dt + \dot{m}(t) \dot{x} dt$,
2. $dv = \dot{\eta} dt$, so $v = \eta$.

Applying integration by parts:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} (m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t)) dt = [m(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t)]_{t_1}^{t_2} - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (m(t) \ddot{x}(t) \eta(t) + \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t)) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.43})$$

The boundary terms $[m(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t)]_{t_1}^{t_2}$ vanish since $\eta(t_1) = \eta(t_2) = 0$, leaving:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} (m(t) \dot{x}(t) \dot{\eta}(t)) dt = - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (m(t) \ddot{x}(t) \eta(t) + \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t)) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.44})$$

Substituting this result back into the variation:

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta x(t)} = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(-m(t) \ddot{x}(t) \eta(t) - \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t) - \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} \right) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.45})$$

For the action to be stationary, this variation must be zero for arbitrary $\eta(t)$. Therefore:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(-m(t) \ddot{x}(t) \eta(t) - \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) \eta(t) - \eta(t) \frac{dU}{dx} \right) dt = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.46})$$

Since this must hold for arbitrary $\eta(t)$, the integrand must be zero:

$$-m(t) \ddot{x}(t) - \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) - \frac{dU}{dx} = 0 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.47})$$

$$m(t) \ddot{x}(t) + \dot{m}(t) \dot{x}(t) = - \frac{dU}{dx} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.48})$$

This is the simplified equation of motion for a particle with a time-dependent mass. The LHS is nothing but force acting on the particle:

$$\vec{F}_x = - \frac{dU}{dx} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.0.0.49})$$

So, we obtained the expected *Newton's* equation. This confirms that the evolution of a system is governed by the principle of stationary action, which provides a solution for the trajectory connecting two points—the initial and final points. Hence, we can apply the same principle to answer the question we initially set up for finding the true trajectory.

One may question the assumption that the initial point is given while the final point is determined only after conducting the experiment. In this case, we identify the endpoints first and then determine the optimized or stationary path between them. Now, consider a scenario where only the initial point is known, and the final point remains unknown in a general sense. How does the ball “know” its final destination to follow the stationary path? It could, in principle, move toward any point and then follow a stationary path from there. To address this question, we must recognize that the principle of stationary action does not imply that a system “knows” its final destination in advance. The system follows local dynamical rules at each instant as how the evolvment takes place in *Newton's* formulation, and the stationary action principle happens to be the consequence and vice versa. This

ensures that, among all possible paths, one outcome takes place. That being said, given the initial conditions, there does not exist stationary path to any final destination point, and it depends only on local dynamics, more precisely given the initial conditions or local dynamics that evolves into a state results in stationary action.

Although we do not yet fully understand the deeper principles behind why this works—at least in classical physics—we have developed alternative framework to Newtonian mechanics. The concept of action is not strictly necessary for describing mechanics; however, in quantum mechanics, it arises naturally. If *Newton's* laws adequately describe a system, why is there a need for an alternative Lagrangian formalism? One key advantage of the Lagrangian formalism is its independence from the choice of coordinate system when solving the equations of motion. This allows for a more flexible approach in dealing with complex systems. To understand this more intuitively, one must explore why this formalism works so well with generalized coordinates. Furthermore, one must ask: Is this formalism applicable only in inertial frames? And how does it apply when the system involves friction?